

LATE PRESENTATION OF A DIAPHRAGMATIC HERNIA AS SMALL BOWEL OBSTRUCTION IN PREGNANCY

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ABSTRACT Spontaneous diaphragmatic hernia without any apparent history of trauma is a rare entity and is very difficult to diagnose. Only a few cases of rupture of the diaphragm without any history of trauma have been recorded in the literature. Diaphragmatic hernias complicating pregnancy are not a common problem, but they can have catastrophic consequences. They can present to the surgeon as a life-threatening emergency or pose a management dilemma when detected incidentally. Complications include volvulus, incarceration, strangulation, haemorrhage and perforation of a hollow viscus. CT scan is the best imaging modality to diagnose diaphragmatic hernias. Surgery is the only treatment of a diaphragmatic hernia in complicate cases irrespective of the status of pregnancy. The majority of these defects can be repaired safely with nonabsorbable sutures without the need for a prosthetic mesh as one in this case.

KEYWORDS Spontaneous diaphragmatic hernia; Intestinal Obstruction; Pregnancy.

INTRODUCTION

A diaphragmatic hernia is usually a congenital disorder, diagnosed either in utero or at birth. A spontaneous diaphragmatic hernia is usually traumatic in origin, but its presence without any apparent history of trauma is even rarer and is very difficult to diagnose. [1] Only a few cases of rupture of the diaphragm without any history of trauma have been recorded in the literature. Early recognition is of utmost importance because delay in the diagnosis may result in an increased morbidity and mortality. [2] We present one such case in a pregnant female presenting as small bowel obstruction.

CASE REPORT

Twenty-six years female came to the emergency department with two days history of pain, abdominal distension with multiple

episodes of bilious vomiting and not passing stools, flatus. She was having 32 weeks+5 days pregnancy. She was 3rd gravida with live births born of normal vaginal delivery and had no similar bowel complaints in the past. The patient was admitted under obstetric department in association with surgery team. Her B.P was 110/80mmhg, pulse 96/min. afebrile maintaining saturation on room air. On examination of her abdomen, gravid uterus occupied the lower abdomen with fundal height reaching up to a point just above the umbilicus with visible distension in the upper abdomen, but abdomen was soft with no tenderness and guarding. Bowel sounds were absent. No visible scar or peristalsis over the abdomen and hernial orifices were normal. Her ultrasound abdomen showed dilated small bowel loops measuring up to 3.4cm with single live foetus in the uterus. Initial diagnosis of small bowel obstruction with pregnancy was made, and conservative management started with nil per oral, intravenous fluids, antibiotics, input & output charting, abdominal girth charting, Ryle's tube insertion to decompress the stomach. On putting the Ryle's tube feculent fluid evacuated (fig. 1) seeing that immediate exploration was planned and it was decided that caesarean section will be performed simultaneously as gynaecology team were doubting foetal distress with intrauterine growth retardation as fundal height was not corresponding to gestation age. The patient was taken up for abdominal exploration with caesarean section through a lower midline incision. A single

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Figure 1: Ryle's tube feculent aspirate.

Figure 4: Greater omentum that was in the defect with small bowel.

Figure 2: Showing dilated and collapsed small bowel loops.

Figure 5: Diaphragmatic defect with heart visible.

Figure 3: Post caesarean sutured uterus.

Figure 6: Closed defect with prolene no. 1.

live male child was delivered, and the uterus was sutured. Then the lower midline incision was extended superiorly to expose whole of the small bowel. Dilated proximal small bowel loops saw with distal loops being collapsed (fig. 2, 3). On tracing the proximal bowel distally, it was seen that a single loop of small bowel with some greater omentum had gone inside the thorax through a midline defect in the diaphragm causing an acute bend and obstruction (fig. 4). On pulling it, the loop with greater omentum came out visualizing the defect which was about 4x 4 cm in size (fig. 5). There was no peritoneal lining forming sac, and through the defect, the heart was seen. Closure of the defect using prolene no. 1 in two layers was done (fig. 6). The small bowel was examined again and was healthy, so abdominal closure was done in layers. Postoperatively patient recovered well, started on a soft diet from day 3 and passed stools on day 4. Sutures were removed on postoperative day 11 and patient was discharged in a comfortable state.

DISCUSSION

A diaphragmatic hernia may be congenital or acquired secondary to thoracoabdominal trauma. In both types, a hernia is most often through the left hemidiaphragm and without a sac. [3] The diaphragm is formed by the fusion of four elements in the embryo: the septum transversum (forming the central tendon); the dorsal oesophageal mesentery; the body wall and the pleuroperitoneal membranes (which close the primitive communication between the pleural and peritoneal cavities). Some defects may occur during development, giving rise to a variety of congenital hernias through the diaphragm. [4] Other than the underlying defect in the pleuroperitoneal canal, the physiological changes of pregnancy and parturition possibly would have facilitated the herniation. In pregnancy, the enlarged gravid uterus not only displaces the bowel to the upper abdomen but also increases the intra-abdominal pressure. The hormonal effect of the pregnancy reduces the tone of the intestinal smooth muscle and slows peristalsis. [5] Constipation is a common problem and chronic straining at defaecation may contribute to laxity of the muscular and ligamentous structure of the diaphragmatic opening or defect. [6] Published reports showed only 36 previously reported cases of diaphragmatic hernias identified during pregnancy. There is a consensus that hernias presenting with evidence of strangulation represent a surgical emergency and mandate operative management, irrespective of foetal maturity. Elective management of asymptomatic hernias is more controversial and both conservative and operative approaches have been suggested. [7] Chest radiograph is a good screening tool, but only 50% of patients show abnormality. CT scan is the best imaging modality to diagnose diaphragmatic hernias. Surgery is the treatment of a diaphragmatic hernia, even in asymptomatic patients. Surgery is described as through thoracic as well as abdominal approach. Treatment by laparoscopy is feasible with a shorter length of stay and least pain. The majority of these defects can be repaired safely with nonabsorbable sutures without the need for a prosthetic mesh as one in this case. [8] Complications of a diaphragmatic hernia include volvulus, incarceration, strangulation, haemorrhage and perforation of a hollow viscus. Prognosis is good in adults (<3% mortality), but poor when complications appear such as organ ischaemic change and haemorrhage. [9]

CONCLUSION

Diaphragmatic hernias can cause life-threatening complications in pregnancy. Consideration should be given to operative repair in the second trimester if asymptomatic hernias are identified during pregnancy. This condition is sporadic and difficult to diagnose unless a very high index of suspicion is kept in mind.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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